

Biodegradable Composite Materials as Bone Regenerative Implants

I. Ahmed, A.J. Parsons, I.A. Jones, G.S. Walker and C.D. Rudd
Biocomposites Group, Faculty of Engineering, Division of Materials Mechanics and Structures, University of Nottingham, Nottingham, NG7 2RD.
Corresponding author email: ifty.ahmed@nottingham.ac.uk

SUMMARY

Biodegradable composites comprising a PCL and PLA matrix have been reinforced with phosphate-based glass fibres and characterised. Fibres were either heat-treated or non-treated, after which they were formed into random mats, alternatively stacked with polymer sheets and compression moulded. Degradation and mechanical studies were conducted on the composites that were produced.

Keywords: *PLA, PCL, Phosphate based glass fibres, physical properties*

INTRODUCTION

Bioresorbable polymers do not provide sufficient load-bearing support within the body as they do not possess the mechanical properties required to fixate bone [1]. Structural implants rely on durable materials such as metal alloys and ceramics which exceed the modulus of the parent bone tissue approximately tenfold. Since bone structure constantly adjusts to local conditions, this tends to weaken surrounding tissues and can result in recurring damage after removal of the device.

Composites comprising a biodegradable polymeric matrix and bioactive fillers have been seen as a promising approach in the field of regenerative medicine, where they have huge possible applications in orthopaedic surgeries for hard tissue repair and reconstruction. These degradable composites have the potential to replace the commonly used metal plates, which have been associated with stress shielding complications. This would eliminate the requirement of a second surgical intervention for implant removal.

It is widely recognised that significant improvements in mechanical properties of polymers can be achieved via fibrous reinforcement. Phosphate-based glasses and fibres (PGF) show great potential as reinforcing materials as they degrade completely in aqueous media [2-3] and their degradation products consist of ions already present within the body (mainly calcium and phosphates) [4].

Andriano et al [5] investigated the biocompatibility screening of three degradable phosphate glass fibres and of several different degradable polymers reinforced with these fibres. It was shown that these composite materials were non-toxic, with no abnormal inflammatory responses observed. However, the glasses used in this study contained varying ions including Al^{3+} .

Lowry et al [6] investigated a PCL/glass bioabsorbable implant in a rabbit humerus fracture model, where it was reported that histological studies showed the materials to be well tolerated with minimal inflammation. The formulation of the glass that was used was not reported.

Long and Rack [7] report the elastic modulus and yield strength of cortical bone as ranging between 10 – 40 GPa and 90 – 140 MPa respectively. In order for an implant to serve primarily as a temporary scaffold for new bone formation, it must have initial properties in or above this range and the rate at which it loses mechanical properties needs to be matched to the rate at which new bone is formed.

In this study, both a PCL and PLA matrix reinforced with phosphate based glass fibres were investigated as potential resorbable devices for bone fracture fixation. Investigations on the mechanical and degradation properties and cytocompatibility have been conducted for a fully degradable iron phosphate-glass fibre polylactic acid (PLA) and binary calcium phosphate polycaprolactone (PCL) composite. Properties of the reinforcing fibres have been obtained along with retention of the mechanical properties over time.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Phosphate Glass, Fibre and Composite Production

Binary calcium phosphate glass fibres (composition 50 P₂O₅ + 50 CaO in mol%) were used to reinforce a PCL matrix. These were made using CaHPO₄ and P₂O₅. The PLA matrix was reinforced with quaternary glass fibres (composition 50 P₂O₅-40 CaO-5 Na₂O-5 Fe₂O₃ in mol%), which were produced by using NaH₂PO₄ and FePO₄·2H₂O in addition to the previous precursors. All the precursors were obtained from Sigma Aldrich, U.K. and used as received. The glass precursors were placed into a 5% Au/95% Pt crucible and dried at 350°C for 30min, before being transferred and melted at 1100°C for 2h in another furnace and then cast at 350°C. Fibres were produced using a specialist made in-house fibre-rig. PCL films were made using pellets purchased from Sigma Aldrich (U.K), whilst the PLA used was obtained from Natureworks (Resin 3051-D, Natureworks®, average Mw ~90,000-120,000). Random fibre mats were produced by a slurry dispersion process and were alternatively stacked with PCL or PLA films into a 170 mm diameter 1.6 mm high round mould cavity, which was then heat-pressed at 38 bar for 20mins at 100°C for PCL and 210°C for PLA.

Mechanical Testing

The initial Young's Modulus and flexural strength were evaluated using the 3 point bending method on a Hounsfield series S testing machine. These studies were conducted in accordance with BS EN ISO 14125:1998. A crosshead speed of 1mm/min was used, with a 1kN load cell.

Degradation Studies

The composites produced were cut into 32 x 15 x 1.6 mm samples and placed into glass vials. Deionised water (30 ml) was added to each of the vials which were then placed into an incubator at 37°C. At various time points, the samples were taken out of their respective containers and excess moisture was removed by blotting the samples dry with tissue. Their new weight was recorded at each time point. The measurements were carried out in triplicate, and the solution (pH adjusted 7.2 ± 0.2 deionised water) was changed at every time point. The data was plotted as percentage weight loss against time.

SEM Analyses

SEM analyses were conducted on the composite samples after completion of the degradation studies. The samples were sputter-coated with gold, and observed using a JEOL 6400 SEM at an accelerating voltage of 20 kV using the SE and BSE images signal.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PCL Composites:

The flexural (3 point-bend) test method was used to obtain initial composite properties (see Figure 1a). No significant improvement in strength was introduced via fibre reinforcement (25-30 MPa). However the modulus showed a 5 fold increase at 18% fibre volume fraction (V_f), from 0.5 to 2.5 GPa. It is well known that short-fibres do not reinforce as effectively as long or continuous fibres due to: (a) the difficulty of controlling orientation and (b) the lower proportion of fibre length carrying full axial stress. In addition, these composites were produced without coupling or sizing agents and a relatively weak interface might be anticipated. The cellulose-based binding agent used to make the random fibre mats did not appear to contribute to the interface development, conferring no property improvements. No explicit measurements of interfacial shear strength (the conventional measure for interface efficiency) are presented here but preliminary results for a similar fibre-matrix combination were published by Slivka et al [8], confirming the above assertions with IFSS values of approximately 15 MPa for CaP / PLLA as compared to 23 MPa for carbon fibre PLLA single fibre composite specimens.

The ultimate compressive strength for trabecular bone from human mandibles ranges from 0.22 to 10.44 MPa. For human vertebra, tibia and femur the strength values range from 0.85 – 5.83 MPa, with modulus values in the range of 1 – 3.2 GPa [9]. The mechanical properties obtained for the composites produced in this study were consistent with values for trabecular bone.

The degradation profiles (Figure 1b) exhibited an ~8% mass loss for the low V_f and approximately 20% mass loss for the 17% and 18% V_f composites. The higher (18%) volume fraction composites tested in this study correlate to approximately 38% by mass of fibres. The plateau exhibited beyond 350 h suggested that most, if not all, of the CaP

glass fibres had degraded and leached into solution. Also, from SEM analyses (Figure 3a) the majority of the fibres appeared to have dissolved, leaving behind some fibre remnants. Therefore, the difference in mass loss compared to mass fraction of fibre was attributed to water residue within the porous structure created upon leaching of the fibres. It was also noted that the as-drawn non treated (NT) and heat-treated (HT) fibre composites yielded very similar degradation profiles (with the non-treated fibre composites starting to degrade very slightly earlier than the heat-treated fibre composites), suggesting that the volume fraction and surface area considerations dominated over the intrinsic behaviour of the fibre when considering fibres of this relatively rapidly degrading glass formulation.

PLA Composites:

The flexural (3 point-bend) test method was also used to obtain the mechanical properties of the PLA composites. Fibre reinforcement was seen to significantly improve both the strength and modulus properties as compared to the polymer alone (see Figure 2a). Studies of POE (poly ortho ester) reinforced with phosphate microfibrils revealed that properties obtained for a 20% volume fraction composite were approximately 90 MPa and 5 GPa for strength and modulus respectively [10]. The initial strength and modulus properties obtained in this study (for approximately 14% fibre V_f composites) were approximately 90 MPa and 5 GPa respectively, which correlated reasonably well with the above studies. The above study also claimed to match the properties of cortical bone using volume loads of 40 to 50%, thus suggesting that the composites produced in this study could also attain cortical bone properties, but with lower fibre volume loads.

From the composite degradation profiles (see Figure 2b) it can be seen that the non-treated fibre composite started to degrade much earlier than the heat-treated fibre composite, whereas no change was observed for the pure PLA samples. This is contrary to that observed for the PCL composites, which is consistent with fibre surface quality tending to dominate in slower degrading fibres. Heat treating phosphate fibres alleviates stresses within the fibres and although this produces an initially weaker fibre, chemical and physical degradation occurs much more slowly [11]. This effect correlated well with the profiles seen from this study where the heat treated fibre composite started to degrade at approximately the 200 hour time point as compared to the non-treated fibre composite, which started to degrade after approximately 48 hours. Although a plateau is observed in the degradation profiles they do still continue to degrade. This was probably due to the resorbable (phosphate) fibres which initially undergo degradation, with the resulting surface acidity around the fibres then contributing to the matrix degradation.

SEM Analyses:

The leaching of fibres from the composites left behind a porous structure. These resulting pores may further facilitate the hydrolytic breakdown of the polymers concerned by allowing passage of water through the structure. It was also noted that for the composites with non-treated fibres, all the fibres had virtually disappeared from within the specimens, whilst for the heat treated fibre specimens, fragments remained visible. These heat treated fibres also exhibited an apparent degradation of the core,

leaving behind an outer shell of fibre. This corresponds to observations made by Choueka et al [11].

There are clear possibilities here to tailor the distribution of porosity within the polymer matrix to serve potential clinical needs. In addition, if the pores contained remnants or residue of the degradation products (i.e. calcium phosphate ions), this may assist in enticing cells from the surrounding tissue to migrate into the resulting porous matrix, and this provides the basis for future studies.

CONCLUSIONS

For PCL (Figures 1a-1b) three composites were produced with non-treated fibres and three with heat-treated fibres. The calculated V_f values were 6.3%, 17% and 18% respectively. The percentage weight loss data showed approx 7-8% weight loss for the 6.3% V_f sample and a 20% weight loss for 17+18% V_f samples, with all 3 composites showing a plateau after 350h. The flexural strength of the composites remained comparable to PCL; however, the modulus increased with increasing volume fraction of fibres from 0.5 GPA (for the PCL matrix alone) to approx 2.5 GPA.

For PLA (Figures 2a-2b) the degradation profiles revealed a 14% mass loss for non-treated and 10% mass loss for the heat-treated fibre composites. Both the heat-treated and non-heat treated composites were of approximately 14% V_f . The flexural strength of the composites matched that of cortical bone; however, the modulus values obtained were lower than required for cortical bone. SEM analyses revealed a porous structure after degradation for both the PCL and PLA composites and it is clear that there are possibilities here to tailor the distribution of porosity within both the polymer matrices investigated.

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Figure 1a: Mechanical properties (flexural tests) obtained for the binary CaP glass fibre PCL composites produced. (Vf = fibre volume fraction, NT = non-treated and HT = heat treated fibres).

Figure 1b: Degradation profiles obtained for the PCL composites produced. (Vf = fibre volume fraction, NT = non-treated and HT = heat treated fibres). Plateau is observed at approximately 350 h.

Figure 2a: Mechanical properties (flexural tests) obtained for quaternary iron-phosphate glass fibre PLA composites produced.

Figure 2b: Degradation profiles obtained for the quaternary iron-phosphate glass fibre PLA composites produced. Earlier degradation is seen for the non-treated fibre composite as compared to the heat-treated fibre composite.

Figure 3a: Higher magnification SEM of fracture surface of heat-treated (HT) PCL fibre composite with 18% Vf. The samples were degraded in glass vials containing 25ml of deionised water at 37°C.

Figure 3b: Fracture surface sample of a heat-treated (HT) PLA / PBG fibre composite after degradation in deionised water at 37°C.

